

Importance of Micronutrients for Soil, Plant, Animal and Human Health

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Introduction

Our planet's survival depends on the precious link between soil and water. Over 95 percent of our food originates from these two fundamental resources. Soil water, vital for nutrient absorption by plants, binds our ecosystems together. This symbiotic relationship is the foundation of our agricultural systems. However, in the face of climate change and human activity, our soils are being degraded, putting excessive pressure on our water resources. Erosion disrupts the natural balance, reducing water infiltration and availability for all forms of life. Sustainable soil management practices, such as minimum tillage, crop rotation, organic matter addition, and cover cropping, improve soil health, reduce erosion and pollution, and enhance water infiltration and storage. These practices also preserve soil biodiversity, improve fertility, and contribute to carbon sequestration, playing a crucial role in the fight against climate change.

Agriculture is the main source of food and nutrients for animals and humans alike. Fertilizers have played a key role in the success of India's Green Revolution and subsequent attainment of self-reliance and sustainability in food-grain production. Demand of fertilizers witnessed double digit growth rates over the past several years in the country on the strength of their 50% contribution to the increase in food production. However, partial factor productivity declined over the years due to accelerated emergence of micronutrient deficiencies in soils. Micronutrients are the essential nutrient elements, albeit required in very small quantities for overall growth of plants. Essential micronutrients involved in plant nutrition are: zinc (Zn), copper (Cu), iron (Fe), manganese (Mn), boron (B), molybdenum (Mo), chlorine (Cl), and nickel (Ni); for animals Zn, Fe, Mn, Cu, selenium (Se), iodine (I) and cobalt (Co) have been identified as being essential; and list for humans includes Zn, Cu, Fe, Mn, Mo, Co, I, Se, fluorine (F), and chromium (Cr). Boron is considered as beneficial trace element for animals and humans both because it prevents losses of Ca and Mg from their bodies. As enshrined in the essentiality criteria, every micronutrient performs specific role in plant, animal and human metabolism and its deficiency/role cannot be mitigated/substituted by any other element. Minerals applied to crops for their nourishment improve their concentration/content in the plant tissues. Inadequate supply of these nutrients in micronutrient deficient soils can lead to loss of yield as well as quality of produce, and consequentially health of animals and humans (Shukla *et al.*, 2018).

Fertility of Indian soils is generally poor exacerbated with progressively emerging micronutrient deficiencies due to their catalyzed removal under agricultural intensification. The Intensification of agriculture-induced whooping nutrient mining of micronutrients from their finite soil resources led to what we experienced in terms of widespread micronutrient deficiencies. Continuous shipping away/export of micronutrients by crops has depleted soil micronutrient reserves and rendered the large tracts of the country deficient in these nutrients. Research evidences suggest that the need-based inclusion of micronutrients in the fertilizer schedules would not only eliminate their deficiencies in soils but also enhance the efficiency of macronutrient fertilizers (Shukla and Behera, 2019). Stagnation in crop productivity can also be eliminated by following balanced fertilization schedule with micronutrients as its essential component. This will ensure reduction in cost of cultivation. Hence, innovative fertilizer products (specialty fertilizers, which include high solubility fertilizer, micronutrient mixtures, slow-release, controlled release, coated, fortified, chelated, organo-mineral, liquid fertilizers, bio-stimulants, bio-based and nanofertilizers) need to be introduced with farmers.

Micronutrients in plant health

Zinc: Zinc plays a key role in plants as a structural constituent or regulatory co-factor of a wide range of different enzymes and proteins. These are mainly concerned with carbohydrate metabolism, both in photosynthesis and in the conversion of sugars to starch, as well as resistance to infection by certain pathogens.

Boron: It aids production of sugar and carbohydrates and essential for seed and fruit development.

Iron: It is essential for chlorophyll formation and key constituent of electron transport chain.

Copper: It is important for reproductive growth and aids in root metabolism and helps in protein utilization.

Manganese: Manganese plays a crucial part in the tricarboxylic acid cycle in oxidation and reduction reactions. It activates several enzymes such as oxidoreductases, hydrolases and lyases. Manganese is a primary component of water-splitting enzyme related to photosystem II.

Molybdenum: it is the structural component of nitrogenase enzyme for nitrogen fixation by rhizobium and essential for absorption and translocation of iron in plants.

Chlorine: It aids plant metabolism and involve in the production of oxygen during photosynthesis.

Nickel: It is the component of urease enzyme and essential for grain development.

Micronutrients in Human health

Micronutrients like Zn and Fe are essential for human health.

Zinc: is vital for more than 300 enzymes in the body and plays a key role in protein synthesis, wound healing, key component of WBC that fight against infections, DNA synthesis, cell division and required for proper sense of taste and smell.

Some of the symptoms of zinc deficiency in humans especially in infants and young children are diarrhoea, pneumonia, stunted growth, weak immune system, retarded mental growth and dwarfism, impaired cognitive function, behavioural problems, memory impairment, problems with spatial learning and neuronal atrophy. The widespread Zn deficiency has led to Zn malnutrition in the humans.

Iron: plays an important role in oxygen transport, DNA synthesis and muscle metabolism. Iron deficiency is the main cause of anaemia. In adults, Fe deficiency including fatigue, impaired physical performance and decreased work productivity.

Micronutrient deficiencies in Soils, Plants, Animals and Humans

Soil

Micronutrient content in soil is dependent on several factors viz., geochemical composition (total micronutrient contents of the soil parent material); soil type (clay mineralogy, particle size distribution, soil horizon, soil age, soil formation processes); intrinsic soil properties like pH, redox potential (Eh), soluble salt concentration (EC); quality and quantity of soil organic matter and calcium carbonate content); inputs of trace elements (supplied through atmospheric deposition, pesticides, manures, fertilizers); available content of macronutrients; micronutrient interactions; and vegetation (Shukla *et al.*, 2016). Indian soils are fairly satisfactory with respect to total micronutrient content. But in spite of the relatively high total contents, micronutrient deficiencies have been frequently reported in many crops due low levels of available micronutrients in soils (Behera and Shukla, 2014; Shukla and Tiwari, 2016). Status of the micronutrients deficiencies was assessed in different soils during 2011-2017. Analysis of more than 2.0 lakhs soil samples during 2011-2017 revealed that on an average, 36.5, 12.8, 4.2, 7.1 and 23.4% soils were deficient in Zn, Fe, Cu, Mn and B, respectively (Table 1).

Plants

Ideal concentrations of micronutrients in plants are 100, 100, 50, 20, 20, 6, 0.1 and 0.1 mg kg⁻¹ of dry matter for Cl, Fe, Mn, B, Zn, Cu, Mo and Ni respectively. Plants show deficiency symptoms or enter the hidden hunger condition when the concentrations of micronutrients fall below their respective critical concentrations (Table 2).

Hidden Hunger

Hidden hunger refers to a situation in which a crop needs more of a given nutrient yet has shown no deficiency symptoms. The nutrient content is above the deficiency symptom zone but still considerably needed for optimum crop production (Fig. 1.) With most nutrients on most crops, significant responses can be obtained even though no recognizable symptoms have appeared.

Fig. 1. Hidden hunger

Table 1. State-wise per cent distribution of micronutrient deficiencies in India

State	Zinc	Iron	Copper	Manganese	Boron
Andhra Pradesh	22.92	17.24	1.33	1.63	4.08
Arunachal Pradesh	4.63	1.44	1.40	3.01	39.15
Assam	28.11	0.00	2.80	0.01	32.75
Bihar	45.25	12.00	3.19	8.77	39.39
Chhattisgarh	25.59	7.06	3.22	14.77	20.59
Goa	55.29	12.21	3.09	16.91	12.94
Gujarat	36.56	25.87	0.38	0.46	18.72
Haryana	15.42	21.72	5.13	6.16	3.27
Himachal Pradesh	8.62	0.51	1.43	6.68	27.02
Jammu & Kashmir	10.91	0.41	0.34	4.60	43.03
Jharkhand	17.47	0.06	0.78	0.26	60.00
Karnataka	30.70	7.68	2.28	0.13	36.79
Kerala	18.34	1.23	0.45	3.58	31.21
Madhya Pradesh	57.05	8.34	0.47	2.25	4.30
Maharashtra	38.60	23.12	0.14	3.02	20.69
Manipur	11.50	2.13	2.46	2.06	37.17
Meghalaya	3.84	1.33	1.03	2.95	47.93
Mizoram	1.96	0.49	0.98	1.22	32.76
Nagaland	4.62	2.00	0.53	3.05	54.31
Odisha	32.12	6.42	7.11	2.12	51.88
Punjab	19.24	13.04	4.67	26.20	18.99
Rajasthan	56.51	34.38	9.15	28.28	2.99
Tamil Nadu	63.30	12.62	12.01	7.37	20.65
Telangana	26.77	16.65	1.36	3.54	16.49
Tripura	5.51	1.57	2.36	0.00	23.62
Uttar Pradesh	27.27	15.56	2.84	15.82	20.61
Uttarakhand	9.59	1.36	1.51	4.82	13.44
West Bengal	14.42	0.03	1.76	0.98	37.05
All India average	36.50	12.8	4.20	7.10	23.4

Table 2. Critical concentration of micronutrients in crop plants

Micronutrients	Crops	Critical concentration (mg kg ⁻¹) for deficiency
Zn	Cereals	15
	Millets	15 - 20
	Legumes	7 - 20
	Vegetables (French bean)	36
	Oilseeds	12 - 25
B	Cereals	4 - 10
	Millets	7 - 15
	Legumes	3 - 15
	Vegetables	3 - 5
	Oilseeds	5 - 10
Mn	Cereals	25
	Millets	10
	Legumes	10-35
	Vegetables	30 - 40
	Oilseeds	5 - 18
Cu	Cereals	2 - 4
	Millets	2 - 3.5
	Legumes	4 - 8
	Vegetables	2 - 6
	Oilseeds	2 - 10

Generalized Visual Leaf and Plant Nutrient Element Deficiency Symptoms

Zinc (Zn)

Deficiency

Upper leaves will show interveinal chlorosis with an eventual whitening of the affected leaves. Leaves may be small and distorted with a rosette form.

Boron (B)

Deficiency

Abnormal development of the growing points (meristematic tissue) with the apical growing points eventually becoming stunted and dying. Rowers and fruits will abort. For some grain and fruit crops, yield and quality is significantly reduced.

Copper (Cu)

Deficiency

Plant growth will be slow and plants stunted with distortion of the young leaves and death of the growing point.

Iron (Fe)

Deficiency

Interveinal chlorosis will occur on the emerging and young leaves with eventual bleaching of the new growth. When severe, the entire plant may be light green in color.

Manganese (Mn)

Deficiency

Interveinal chlorosis of young leaves while the leaves and plants remain generally green in color. When severe, the plants will be stunted.

Molybdenum (Mo)

Deficiency

Symptoms will frequently appear similar to N deficiency. Older and middle leaves become chlorotic first, and In some instances, leaf margins are rolled and growth and flower formation are restricted.

Chlorine (Cl)

Deficiency

Younger leaves will be chlorotic and plants will easily wilt. For wheat, a plant disease will infest the plant when Cl is deficient.

The visual micronutrient deficiency symptoms in major crops are shown in Fig. 2.

Zn deficiency in rice	Cu deficiency in rice
Mn deficiency in groundnut	Fe deficiency in sugarcane
B deficiency in coconut	B deficiency in cabbage
Mo deficiency in cabbage	Mo deficiency in cauliflower

Fig. 2. Visual micronutrient deficiency symptoms in major crops

Animals

Uptake of mineral nutrients by crops and pastures from soil is influenced by several factors such as soil types and their properties like soil acidity, soil moisture content, temperature, climatic condition, crop type and variety, crop management practices, application of fertilizer and organic matter and microbial activity of soil etc. Among the factors, soil acidity plays pivotal role in influencing trace mineral uptake by the crops and pastures. Higher soil pH leads to an enhanced biological availability of some trace elements such as Se and Mo, whereas with lower soil pH, availability of Se is less. But the uptake of some cationic trace elements like Cu is increased. Sometimes, the level of Cu, Zn, Mn, Fe and Co in crops is sufficient for optimum yields but is not adequate to meet the needs of livestock animals.

Humans

Good human health is linked with healthy soils, which produce variety of food. Estimated 40% of the world's population, mostly in low income countries is facing a problem of micronutrient malnutrition. Burgeoning rise in the number of the people affected with micronutrient malnutrition during last four decades in India coincides with expansion of the area under rice-wheat or rice-rice cropping systems (low nutritional quality food) having high yielding varieties (HYVs) at the expense of traditional cereal-pulses/legume (high nutritional quality food) systems. Dietary intake ought to be changed with increased consumption of pulses to ensure adequate and balanced micronutrient supply to one and all in an affordable manner (Welch *et al.*, 1997). Widespread prevalent nutritional deficiencies of vitamin A, Fe, Zn, and iodine have been adversely influencing the health of women and young children. Shortage of micronutrients in the diet can limit growth, weaken immunity, cause xerophthalmia (an irreversible eye disorder leading to blindness), and increase mortality. Neutropenia and leucopenia, skeletal defects and degradation of nervous system (Prasad, 1961), defective melanin synthesis, which manifests as depigmentation or hypopigmentation (lack of colour) of hair and skin, keratinization of hair, steely hair are other signs of micronutrient deficiencies in the humans (Davis and Mertz, 1987).

In general, agriculture is the primary supplier of food and nutrients to all human on earth. The biggest challenge is to feed and nourish a burgeoning human population with limited land resources for productive agriculture. In addition, multimicronutrient deficiencies in soils worldwide leading to production of poor quality crop produce, particularly low in trace elements, ultimately affect the animal and human health (Shukla *et al.*, 2014, 2016; Behera and Shukla, 2014). Toxicity of trace elements (particularly Fe, Al, Se, As, F, Cr etc.) in soil and water may also affect animal and human health.

Zinc

The available Zn in Indian soils ranges from 0.01 to 52.9 mg kg⁻¹. It constitutes less than 1% of the total Zn content. Currently 36.5% of soil samples across the country are deficient in available Zn; about 8, 29 and 15% area of the country is suffering from acute deficiency, deficiency and latent deficiency of Zn, respectively (Fig. 3.). Acute Zn-deficient soils are intensively cultivated ones characterized by coarse texture (sandy/ loamy sand), high pH (> 8.5 or alkali/ sodic soils) and/or calcareousness, and low soil organic carbon (< 0.4%) content (Shukla *et al.*, 2014). Zinc deficiency disorders are known by different nomenclatures like 32khaira disease in rice, rosetting in wheat, white bud in maize, little leaves and mottling in vegetables, and reduced fruit formation in citrus.

Fig.3. Available zinc status in soils of India

Feed and fodders produced on micronutrient-deficient soils and fed to cattle in Haryana resulted in higher percentage of Zn, Cu and Mn deficiency in their blood serum, hair and milk (Table 3). Survey in Vadodara district of Gujarat showed that dry fodder tested low in Fe (61%), Zn (72%) and Cu (87%) and green fodders were low in Fe (17%), Zn (5%) and Cu (23%) although most of the soils on which this was grown were adequate in terms of available Fe, Mn and Cu. A specific disorder resulting from zinc deficiency in animals is parakeratosis – a disorder of the epidermal layer of the skin occurring in calves, sheep, goats and piglets. Phytate (inositol hexaphosphate): Zn ratio plays an important role in influencing the Zn bioavailability in animal body. Excess intake of Zn is relatively rare in farm animals. However, excess zinc may reduce the digestibility of phosphorus, and cause anemia and digestive disorders. Poisoning is conditioned primarily by the antagonistic relationship of zinc with iron and copper. Excessive intake of Zn additives may lead to the essential fatty acid metabolism which influences synthesis of prostaglandin.

Table 3. Average percentage of mineral nutrient deficiency in blood serum, hair and milk in cattle of Haryana

Deficiency percentage based on	Cu	Zn	Mn
Serum mineral status	40.0	-	
Hair mineral status basis	-	50.3	47.6
Milk mineral status basis	29.0	42.9	

In humans, Zn deficiency was recognized as a health concern for the first time in 1961. The human Zn deficiency syndromes are growth stunting, delayed sexual development and hypogonadism in young adults Besides, Zn deficiency leads to diarrhoea, respiratory malfunctions, weak immune system, impaired cognitive function, neuronal atrophy, behavioural problems, memory impairment, spatial learning, lesions on dermal tissue/keratin (Fig. 4.) and parakeratosis. In general, a very strong correlation has been reported between soil Zn status and human Zn deficiency level (Singh, 2009; Shukla *et al.*, 2016).

Fig. 4. Zinc deficiency symptoms in humans

Iron

In India, the problem of iron deficiency mainly occurs in calcareous and alkaline soils with $\text{pH} > 7.5$. Availability of Fe gets aggravated under drought or moisture stress conditions due to conversion of ferrous form of iron (Fe^{2+}) into less available ferric form (Fe^{3+}). hinder iron availability to the crop plants. About 4, 9 and 6% area of the country is inflicted with acute deficiency, deficiency and latent deficiency of Fe, respectively (Fig. 5). About 10, 11 and 60% area is characterized by adequate, high and very high levels of available Fe, respectively. Strongly acid and waterlogged soils have very high level of available Fe. There is a peculiar problem in flooded (paddy) rice soils where rice yields get severely reduced by Fe toxicity. Iron chlorosis in plants, also called lime-induced chlorosis, is generally observed in upland crops especially aerobic rice, sorghum, groundnut, sugarcane, chick pea grown in Fe-deficient highly calcareous soils, compact soil with restricted aeration, soils with low in active Fe and high in P and bicarbonate content. (Takkar *et al.*, 1989; Singh and Dayal, 1992).

Fig. 5. Available iron status in soils of India

Iron is one of the most abundant element (4th at 5%) on Earth. Globally, Fe-deficiency anemia is the most common widespread nutritional disorder, affecting more than 50% pregnant women and 40% of infants and preschool children. Although only 14.4% Indian soils are deficient in available Fe, iron deficiency anaemia (IDA) is quite acute and widespread in marginalised section of our country.

The low Fe content in forage and food grains produced in arid and semi-arid regions is attributed to acute Fe deficiency in these soils (34% in Rajasthan, 26% in Gujarat, 22% in Haryana, and 23% in Maharashtra). However, in some humid and subhumid regions of the country where Fe is in sufficient amount in soil, increased IDA may be attributed to poor accumulation of Fe in plants grown on these soils. For example, IDA is very high in north-eastern region of the country where about 84.9% women reportedly suffer from IDA due to rice-based diet, as rice is a poor accumulator of Fe.

Copper

Copper deficiency in Indian soils is almost negligible. Available Cu content in Indian soils ranges from 0.01 to 136.4 mg kg⁻¹ with an average value of 2.05 mg Cu kg⁻¹ (Shukla and Tiwari, 2016). About 2, 2 and 3% area of the country is having acute deficiency, deficiency and latent deficiency of Cu, respectively (Fig. 5). Copper availability is mainly influenced by pH, SOC, CaCO₃ and clay content in soils. It increases with increase in organic matter and clay content, while decreases with increase in pH and CaCO₃ content of the soil (Katyal and Agarwal, 1982; Rattan *et al.*, 1999). Copper deficiency mainly occurs in sandy, calcareous, eluviated and organic matter-rich soils. Addition of organic matter releases the CaCO₃-bound Cu fraction in soil and rebind it in organic fraction, enhancing the Cu availability in calcareous and sandy loam soils. However, presence of excess organic matter reduces the Cu availability in organic peat soils (Histosols) of Kerala, hill (Alfisols) and submontane soils (Mollisols) of the Himalayan tarai zone of Uttarakhand and Himachal Pradesh (Singh, 2008; Patel *et al.*, 2009; Behera *et al.*, 2012).

Fig. 6. Available iron status in soils of India

In India, Cu deficiency is responsible for leucoderma (Vitiligo), depigmentation of hair and skin around the neck, face, hind limbs and abdomen in buffaloes. Copper deficiency also caused ‘falling disease’ in milch cows. Copper concentrations in the livers of affected animals was lower (32.6 mg kg^{-1}) as compared to healthy cow (55.7 mg kg^{-1}) (Vasudevan, 1987). Post parturient haemoglo-binuria (PPH), molybdenosis induced hypocupraemia, commonly referred as nutritional haemoglobinuria, was observed, in high yielding cattle and buffaloes in India (Dhillon and Dhillon, 1991; Singh and Randhawa, 1990).

Copper deficiency in human leads to hypocupraemia, neutropenia and leucopenia, degradation in nervous system, skeletal defects, hypopigmentation of hair and skin, keratinization of hair, cardiovascular disorders, osteoporosis, arthritis and infertility (Davis and Mertz, 1987).

Manganese

The available Mn content varies from 0.01 to 445.0 mg kg^{-1} with a mean value of 21.8 mg kg^{-1} (Shukla *et al.*, 2014). About 1, 6 and 10% area of the country suffers from acute deficiency, deficiency and latent deficiency of Mn, respectively (Fig. 7). In general, Mn deficiency problems occur on soils with low total contents of Mn (heavily weathered tropical and sandy soils), on peaty soils, or organic-rich soils with a pH above 6, and on mineral soils with pH values of 6.5 or above, calcareous soils, or acid soils which have been heavily limed. In India, incidence of Mn deficiency has increased very fast, particularly in rice–wheat cropping systems under sandy or loamy sand soils of Punjab and Haryana. Mn is more mobile in imperfectly drained soils (waterlogged) and often Mn toxicity is observed in rice grown under continuous submerged conditions on such soils. Deficiency of Mn results in appearance of greenish-grey specks at the lower base of younger leaves in monocots, which finally become yellowish to yellow-orange. It may lead to development of marsh spots (necrotic areas) on the cotyledon of legumes. In sugarcane, Mn deficiency is called as pahala blight.

Fig. 7. Available manganese status in soils of India

Crops like wheat grown in Mn deficient soils or hidden hunger of Mn in Haryana not only produced low yields but led to infertility in cattle due to low Mn content in fodder and grain. Evidence of increased infertility was recorded in cattle fed with low Mn fodder grown in highly calcareous soils (free CaCO₃ content 20-48%) (Singh, 2009). Productivity of these animals was low and their blood serum Mn concentration was also low as compared to that in cattle fed with fodders grown in Mn-adequate soils.

Boron

In India, extent of B deficiency is next only to Zn. Total B content in Indian soils ranges from 2.6 to 630 mg kg⁻¹ (Takkar, 2011) and available (hot water soluble – HWS) B ranges from 0.04 to 250 mg B kg⁻¹, with an average of 21.9 mg kg⁻¹ soil (Shukla and Tiwari, 2016). About 4, 19 and 21% area of the country faces acute deficiency, deficiency and latent deficiency of B, respectively (Figure 8). Availability of B to plants is governed by soil pH, CaCO₃ and organic matter contents. In addition total B content in soil, its interactions with other nutrients, plant type or variety and environmental factors also have strong influence on B availability.

Fig. 8. Available boron status in soils of India

B deficiency adversely impacts the crop productivity in highly calcareous soils, sandy leached soils, limed acid soils or reclaimed yellow or lateritic soils. In general, extent of B

deficiency is higher in eastern region of the country due to its excess leaching in sandy loam soils because of high rainfall (Takkar, 1996; Shukla and Behera, 2012; Shukla and Tiwari, 2016). Boron deficiency symptoms first appear on the growing tips and younger leaves with stunted plant growth. It results in production of hollow heart in peanut, black heart in beet, distorted and lumpy fruit in papaya, and hollow pith in cabbage and cauliflower. B in various physiological functions, especially in improving the utilization of bone forming minerals like calcium, phosphorus and magnesium, immunity and antioxidant defence mechanisms (Bhasker *et al.*, 2016). Boron supplementation in farm animals enhanced the immunity by increasing the serum levels of tumour necrosis factor and interferon-gamma. Further B supplementation lowered the levels of serum triglycerides, HDL cholesterol, ALT and ameliorated the hepatic tissue alterations induced by the lower Ca intake, thus exhibiting hepato-protective effect (Bhasker *et al.*, 2017).

Molybdenum

Molybdenum is least studied micronutrients in India. Total Mo in Indian soils ranges between 0.1 to 12 mg kg⁻¹ and available Mo, extracted with ammonium oxalate (pH 3.3), varies from traces to 2.8 mg kg⁻¹ (Behera *et al.*, 2011, 2014). Molybdate anions (MoO₄²⁻) are strongly adsorbed on soil minerals and colloids (at pH < 6.0) and sometimes are also trapped due to formation of secondary minerals. Hydrated aluminium silicates may also strongly fix Mo. Soils formed from shale and granite parent materials have high Mo concentrations, whereas those derived from sandstone, basalt and limestone are characterized by low Mo contents. Most of the soils are adequate in Mo but its deficiency is noticed in some acidic, sandy and leached soils. Its deficiency is rarely reported in calcareous alkaline soils of arid and semi-arid regions as these soils have fairly high available Mo contents. Molybdenum deficiencies severely affect legumes, crucifer vegetables and oilseed crops on acid and severely leached soils. Molybdenum deficiency results in stunted plant growth and restricted flower formation. It causes whiptail disease of cauliflower. Molybdenum deficiency is reported in eastern high rainfall zone soils low in available Mo. In northern parts of West Bengal, problem of hair and hooves falling in cattle has been reported widely due to low Mo in alluvial leached soils. Grain legumes have higher concentration of Mo. In human, Mo helps in breakdown of build-up of toxic compounds such as sulphites. Molybdenum has been shown to help fight cancer-causing nitrosamines and even assists in preventing cavities. The most associated function of molybdenum is its role in the production of uric acid. Adequate Mo prevents dental caries, mouth and gum disorders, oesophageal cancer, and sexual impotence in old people.

Zinc in Soil-Plant-Animal/Human Continuum – A Case Study

A systematic study on Zn in soil-plant-animal/human continuum was carried out jointly by AICRP - MSPE and AIIMS, Bhopal in two tribal districts of Madhya Pradesh to assess the relationship between soil and human health (Shukla *et al.*, 2018). Analysis of Zn content in soil, grain, straw feed, animal and human blood serum established a strong correlation and interdependence among soil-plant-animal-human continuum (Fig. 9). The results indicated a strong relationship of soil Zn with plant and human blood serum Zn. The coefficient of determination (R^2) were 0.36 between soil Zn content and grain Zn concentration, and 0.48 between Zn concentration in human blood serum and grain Zn concentration. However, no significant relationship was observed between straw Zn content and animal blood serum Zn concentration. When contribution of Zn through feed and Zn content in grazing grass was included with fodder Zn content, significant relationship emerged with animal blood serum Zn ($R^2 = 0.61$).

Fig. 9. Relationship between soil, plant, animal and human Zn

Zinc and Covid 19

Zinc played a critical role in boosting immunity in human beings to fight deadly diseases like Covid-19 during pandemic. Widespread deficiency of Zn in human population has resulted in poor immunity to fight against diseases (Soumitra Das and Andrew Green, 2023). Many Indians have a lower intake of Zn than the required levels for optimal immune function. Zinc deficiency often makes people more susceptible to flu, cold and viral infections. A several lack of zinc can massively reduce the activity of immune cells and production of antibodies. Adult body contains 2-3 g of Zn and a daily intake of up to 15 mg of Zn is needed to maintain a steady state as there is no Zn storage system in the body.

Micronutrients and Food grain production

An increasing trend in consumption of micronutrient fertilizers and production of food grains plus oilseeds reveals that the importance of micronutrients for sustainable crop production.

Micronutrients requirement for agricultural and horticultural crops in India are shown in Table 4. The current requirement of different micronutrients has been calculated based on current level of deficiency, nutrient mining from the soil and micronutrient recommendations for different crops. The future recommendations have been estimated based on area likely to be deficient and enhanced crop requirement due to intensification of agriculture by 2035 and 2050 (Shukla *et al.*, 2021). Of the total Zn used, 70% used for field crops and remaining 30% to vegetables and fruit crops, while the reverse in case of Mn, Fe and Cu. Of the total B application, about 60% is applied to vegetables and fruit crops and 40% to food grain and oilseed crops.

Table 4. Micronutrient requirement for agricultural and horticultural crops in India

Micronutrients	Micronutrient requirements ('000 tons)		
	2020	2035	2050
Zn	285	147	402
B	129	147	167
Fe	177	193	216
Mn	118	127	138
Cu	29	31	34

Strategies to Improve Micronutrient Nutrition in Animals and Humans

Issues pertaining to deficiency and toxicity of micronutrients in animal and human health emanate from low and very high flow of these elements to animals and humans through the soil-water-plant-animal-human food chain in different geographical areas. Soil is the major source supplying micro-nutrient elements to food chain. Cereals namely, rice and wheat grown in Zn- and Fe deficient soils produce grains in low Zn and Fe content. Consequently, the cereal-based food/diet, that contributes 70 % of the daily calorie intake of the poor population, is also low in Zn and Fe concentration. The approaches used to manage and/or prevent Fe and Zn deficiency and improve their status in humans are as follows.

Supplementation

Oral use of Fe and Zn tablets, capsules, and emulsions alone or in combination with vitamins as per the prescription of physicians and nutritionists is effective in mitigating the deficiencies of iron and zinc.

Fortification

Adding Fe and Zn to foods, such as flour, bread, biscuits, milk, salt, weaning food etc. has been

recognized as an effective approach to improve micronutrient level and alleviate their deficiency in humans as per Copenhagen Consensus of 2012. Fortification is effective in increasing micronutrient concentration in serum. Hematologic markers, including haemoglobin concentrations, showed a significant rise when food was fortified with vitamin A, iron and

multiple micronutrients. Fortification with zinc had no significant adverse impact on haemoglobin levels. Multiple micronutrient fortification showed non-significant impacts on height for age, weight for age and weight for height Z-scores, although they indicated the positive trends. Iron fortification led to a significant increase in serum ferritin and haemoglobin levels in women of reproductive age and pregnant women.

Dietary Diversification

The foods with the highest concentration of Fe, Zn and vitamin A are generally animal meats, fish, egg, pulses, whole grains, millets, nuts, legumes, and yeast (Table 5). Although dietary diversification is a potential preventive approach to improve Fe and Zn status and reduce their deficiency in the humans, but it is very expensive and beyond the purchasing capacity of the poor population vulnerable to the risk of micronutrient malnutrition.

Table 5. Major dietary sources and substances promote Fe, Zn and vitamin A bioavailability

Major dietary sources	Promoter substance	Nutrient
Fresh fruits and vegetables	Organic acids	Fe and /or Zn
Animal meats	Haemoglobin	Fe
Animal meats	Amino acids	Fe and /or Zn
Human breast milk	Long-chain fatty acids	Zn
Animal fats, vegetable fats	Fats and lipids	Vitamin A
Sea foods, Tropical nuts	Selenium	Iodine
Animal meats	Iron, zinc	Vitamin A
Coloured vegetables	β -carotene	Fe, Zn
Garlic, Onion, Wheat	Insulin and other non-digestible carbohydrates	Ca, Fe and Zn

Producing Micronutrient-rich Food

Production of micronutrient-rich food involving genetic modification in crops and change in fertilizer strategies through innovative agricultural interventions such as biofortification, offers a sustainable solution to tackle micronutrient malnutrition in the poverty-ridden population.

Genetic Biofortification

Genetic biofortification is a seed-based approach where the germ plasm is enriched with specific nutrients: micronutrients, protein, amino acids etc. It can be done by conventional breeding, marker driven molecular breeding, or genetic engineering. Some of the promising products of this approach are Zn- and Fe- rich rice, wheat and maize. Golden rice rich in beta-carotene, high Fe rice (high ferritin gene from mangroves) are examples of genetic engineering for bio fortification.

Agronomic Biofortification

Agronomic biofortification is an inexpensive and simple approach which can be utilized to enrich the genetically-inefficient cultivars by application of micronutrient fertilizers at different rates, methods and at different crop growth stages.

Physiological Intervention

Accumulation of micronutrients in edible portion of seeds is controlled by physiological and biochemical barriers in plants. These barriers are the result of tightly controlled homeostatic mechanisms that regulate metal absorption, translocation, and redistribution in plants allowing adequate, but nontoxic levels of these nutrients to accumulate in plant tissues. **Nipping** (apical bud removal) and defoliation (25% leaf removal) are two important practices to change the physiology of legume crops. Plant releases greater amount of soluble organic acids, phytosiderophores, enzymes and reductants or oxidants to recoup from injury caused by nipping and defoliation. It has been observed that nipping and defoliation practices could enhance Fe concentration both in efficient and inefficient cultivars of chickpea and pigeon pea (Shukla et al., 2016). **Defoliation** (25% of leaves) at pre-flowering stages could enhance the Fe concentration in grain by 7 and 4%, respectively in efficient and inefficient cultivars.

Soil Health Improvement technologies developed at TNAU

Soil Test Crop Response based Integrated Plant Nutrition System (STCR-IPNS) and Secondary and Micronutrients recommendation

All these problems can be rectified by better management options and application of amendments and the current challenge is to adopt economically and ecologically sound management strategies like Soil Test Crop Response based Integrated Plant Nutrition System (STCR-IPNS) for achieving crop productivity, nutrient use efficiency, profitability with sustained soil health. It involves application of nutrients through inorganic fertilisers, organic manures and biofertilizers based on soil fertility status and yield targets. Ready reckoner of fertiliser doses and secondary and micronutrient recommendations for principal crops are provided in CPG Agriculture 2020 and CPG Horticulture 2020.

- ❖ **Major nutrient recommendations (STCR-IPNS) :** 37 crops & 10 cropping sequences
- ❖ **Secondary & Micronutrients recommendations:** 44 crops & 10 cropping sequences

Benefits over Blanket recommendations/Farmers' fertilization practice

- ❖ **Yield increase:** 15-25% in Agricultural crops & 25-35% in Horticultural crops
- ❖ **Rationalized Fertilizer usage**
 - **Saving in high fertile soils: 25-50% for NPK**

- Fertilizer saving: FP_{205} & FK_{20} : 26 & 25 kg ha⁻¹ saving for rice under Noyyal series in terms of SSP: 193 tonnes & MOP: 49 tonnes due to built up over initial status if SP & SK are 28 & 438 kg ha⁻¹.

❖ Secondary and Micronutrients fertilization only in deficient areas

Decision Support System for Integrated Fertiliser Recommendation (DSSIFER)

Decision Support System for Integrated Fertiliser Recommendation (DSSIFER) is a user friendly software developed in Visual Basic 6.0 as a “Stand Alone” version encompasses soil test crop response based fertiliser recommendations through Integrated Plant Nutrition System (STCR-IPNS) developed by the ICAR-AICRP-STCR, Department of Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry, TNAU and Mitscherlich-Bray

percentage sufficiency recommendations developed by the Soil Testing Wing of the State Department of Agriculture, Tamil Nadu. **If both recommendations are not available** for a particular soil – crop situation, **the software can generate prescriptions using blanket recommendations but based on soil test values.** Therefore, adoption of this technology will not only ensure site specific balanced fertilisation to achieve targeted yield of crops but also result in correction of inherent soil nutrient deficiencies, higher response ratio, minimizing nutrient losses besides sustaining soil fertility. In addition, the software also provides technology for **problem soil management and irrigation water quality appraisal.**

Visual Diagnostic Kit (VDK)

The computer software Visual Diagnostic Kit (VDK) aids in identifying nutrient deficiencies of crops. It has documentation of deficiency symptoms of 65 crops.

Both DSSIFER and VDK softwares are of much use for all the Soil Testing Laboratories of State Department of Agriculture, KVKs, Agrilclinic cum Mini Soil Testing Laboratories at each block level, Soil Testing Laboratories of PACBs, NGOs, private entrepreneurs, scientists, research scholars, progressive farmers for identifying deficiency symptoms, prescribing fertiliser doses and soil and water quality management technologies. This is being used in the Soil Testing and Technology Advisory centre (SOTAC) of Department of Soil Science and Agricultural

Chemistry, TNAU, Coimbatore for providing analytical and advisory services to the farmers and other stakeholders.

TNAU Crop Specific Micronutrient Mixtures

Micronutrients use efficiency is abysmally low and generally does not exceed 5% in crops. Development of new and innovative micronutrient fertilizer products for higher use efficiency is the need of the hour. In this context,

- Micronutrient mixtures were developed by the Department of Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry, TNAU for 11 major crops viz., Rice, Maize, Pulses, Groundnut, Sunflower, Gingelly, Castor, Cotton, Sugarcane, Turmeric and Coconut for both irrigated and rainfed situations and the following recommendations are being adopted.
- Application of MN mixtures as Enriched FYM will help to tackle the multi-micronutrient deficiency problems besides balanced fertilization to crop.
- Indirect benefits: Balanced fertilization of crops through fertilizer mixtures will ensure enhanced crop productivity besides sustaining soil fertility.

The recommendation of TNAU Crop specific micronutrient mixtures for various crops are given in table 5.

Table 5. TNAU Crop specific Micronutrient Mixtures Recommendation for various crops

S. No	Crop	Dosage (kg ha ⁻¹)	
		Irrigated	Rainfed
1.	Rice - wetland	25.0	-
	Rainfed	-	12.5
2.	Maize	30.0	7.5
3.	Pulses	5.0	5.0
4.	Sugarcane	50.0	-
5.	Cotton	Variety - 12.5	7.5
		Hybrid - 15.0	
6.	Groundnut	12.5	7.5
7.	Gingelly	12.5	7.5
8.	Sunflower	12.5	7.5
	Hybrid	15.0	10.0
9.	Castor	12.5	7.5
	Hybrid	15.0	10.0
10.	Turmeric	Split application of 15 kg TNAU Micronutrients mixture as EFYM at 50 %	

		basal and 50 % top dressing on 90 DAP	
11.	Coconut varieties/hybrid	1 kg / tree / year	-

Cost of TNAU MN Mixture: Rs. 130/kg (Including GST)

Method of application: As basal soil application

- TNAU MN mixture (at the recommended dose for each crop) is to be thoroughly mixed with FYM @ 1:10 ratio at friable moisture condition and incubated for 15 to 30 days under shade)
- For Turmeric, Split application of 15 kg TNAU Micronutrients mixture as EFYM at 50 % basal and 50 % top dressing on 90 DAP for irrigated turmeric

TNAU-Water Soluble Fertilizer (TNAU-WSF)

Water Soluble Fertilizers are essential for efficient and balanced use of fertilizer nutrients. They are 100 per cent water soluble and suitable for fertigation of all crops and soil types. Higher fertilizer use efficiency, crop yields and more profit to the farmers. TNAU has established pilot WSF production unit at TNAU, Coimbatore and supplying TNAU WSF All 19 @ Rs. 200/kg.

Nutri seed /Nutri pellet Packs

Nutrised Pack contains seed at top, enriched manure in the middle and encapsulated fertilizer at bottom. Nutrised Packs are meant for single time placement in soil at the time of sowing to act as nutrient pile for slow release of nutrients. Nutrised Pack gives support for each plant in the root zone in terms of optimum nutrient supply, biological activity and consequently enables the fullest utilization of nutrients by plants. There is no wastage of fertilizer nutrients with Nutrised Packs.

Conclusion

The widespread occurrence of micronutrient malnutrition can be solved by food supplementation, food fortification and biofortification. Biofortification is the best option for alleviation of multi nutrient deficiency. Soil Test Crop Response - Integrated Plant Nutrition system (STCR-IPNS) is a pivotal approach, offering a multifaceted strategy to enhance the

efficacy of fertilizer use and maintenance of soil fertility Hence, there is a balanced supply of required quantities of nutrients to the crop thereby over usage or under usage is avoided. This prevents environmental hazards and results in higher net returns.

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